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Predicting speech intelligibility from a selective attention decoding paradigm in cochlear implant users

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E-mail: nogueiravazquez.waldo@mh-hannover.de**Keywords:** cochlear implant, selective attention, electroencephalography, prediction speech understanding performance, neural tracking

Abstract

Objectives. Electroencephalography (EEG) can be used to decode selective attention in cochlear implant (CI) users. This work investigates if selective attention to an attended speech source in the presence of a concurrent speech source can predict speech understanding in CI users. **Approach.** CI users were instructed to attend to one out of two speech streams while EEG was recorded. Both speech streams were presented to the same ear and at different signal to interference ratios (SIRs). Speech envelope reconstruction of the to-be-attended speech from EEG was obtained by training decoders using regularized least squares. The correlation coefficient between the reconstructed and the attended (ρ_{ASIR}) or the unattended (ρ_{USIR}) speech stream at each SIR was computed. Additionally, we computed the difference correlation coefficient at the same ($\rho_{Diff} = \rho_{ASIR} - \rho_{USIR}$) and opposite SIR ($\rho_{DiffOpp} = \rho_{ASIR} - \rho_{U-SIR}$). ρ_{Diff} compares the attended and unattended correlation coefficient to speech sources presented at different presentation levels depending on SIR. In contrast, $\rho_{DiffOpp}$ compares the attended and unattended correlation coefficients to speech sources presented at the same presentation level irrespective of SIR. **Main results.** Selective attention decoding in CI users is possible even if both speech streams are presented monaurally. A significant effect of SIR on ρ_{ASIR} , ρ_{Diff} and $\rho_{DiffOpp}$, but not on ρ_{USIR} , was observed. Finally, the results show a significant correlation between speech understanding performance and ρ_{ASIR} as well as with ρ_{USIR} across subjects. Moreover, $\rho_{DiffOpp}$ which is less affected by the CI artifact, also demonstrated a significant correlation with speech understanding. **Significance.** Selective attention decoding in CI users is possible, however care needs to be taken with the CI artifact and the speech material used to train the decoders. These results are important for future development of objective speech understanding measures for CI users.

1. Introduction

A cochlear implant (CI) is a small implantable medical device that can restore the hearing sense to people suffering from severe or profound hearing loss. The CI bypasses the damaged structures of the inner ear by directly stimulating the auditory nerve. Although most CI users obtain good speech intelligibility in quiet environments, their speech recognition deteriorates in environments containing noise or competing talkers (e.g. Cullington and Zeng 2008). For this reason, it is essential to program the CI to optimize its outcome. The outcome is usually measured as

the number of correctly understood words from a clinical speech test, in which words are presented and the CI user is asked to repeat the recognized words. However, these tests are difficult to perform in people with fluctuating engagement (i.e. children) or with absent response (i.e. unconscious patients or subjects with additional disabilities). For this reason, several objective paradigms have been proposed to predict the speech performance of CI users that do not require the behavioral response of the tested subject (e.g. Gransier *et al* 2016, Verschueren *et al* 2018). Such paradigms could find application to speed up the fitting procedure, to automatically optimize the speech

performance of CI users and to track the speech performance of CI users objectively across time.

In this context, several objective peripheral and cortical measures based on electroencephalography (EEG) have been proposed to assess hearing performance. These measures include auditory brainstem responses (e.g. Verhaert *et al* 2008, Anderson *et al* 2013), auditory steady state responses (ASSRs; e.g. Picton *et al* 2005, Luts *et al* 2006, Gransier *et al* 2016), cortical auditory evoked potentials (e.g. Sharma and Dorman 2006, Liebscher *et al* 2018), acoustic change complex (e.g. Undurraga *et al* 2021) or P300/mismatch negativity (e.g. Roman *et al* 2005, Martin *et al* 2008). More specifically, ASSRs have been found to highly correlate with speech understanding performance in CI users (Gransier *et al* 2020), however its predictive power may be limited by the use of simple auditory stimuli (Lesenfants *et al* 2019).

For this reason, it has been suggested that measures of brain activity based on EEG neural tracking to natural running speech can provide a more realistic and objective measure of speech understanding performance (e.g. Ding and Simon 2012, Vanthornhout *et al* 2018). In neural tracking, the brain responses can be decoded from the speech signal with the so called forward model (Haufe *et al* 2014). Using this method, a temporal response function (TRF) can be derived in which interpretable peaks, such as the N1 and the P2 can be observed (Lalor *et al* 2009, Petersen *et al* 2016, di Liberto *et al* 2018). In contrast, the backward model can be used to reconstruct the speech envelope from the recorded EEG. The correlation coefficient between the original and the reconstructed speech stream is used as a measure of neural coding of speech. Previous studies used neural tracking methods in which the listener was asked to attend and to understand the speech uttered by a single speaker. Recently, it was proposed that the correlation coefficient derived from a neural tracking paradigm can predict speech understanding performance in normal hearing (NH) listeners (e.g. Ding and Simon 2013, Ding *et al* 2014, di Liberto *et al* 2018, Vanthornhout *et al* 2018, 2019, Lesenfants *et al* 2019, Decruy *et al* 2020). Indeed, it was shown that higher correlation coefficients are observed when the presented speech is more understandable for the listeners (Dimitrijevic *et al* 2019, Etard *et al* 2019). More recently, it has been shown that the correlation coefficient of neural tracking at late cortical processing can predict speech understanding performance in bilateral CI users (Paul *et al* 2020). However, in CI users it is necessary to suppress the CI artifact (Somers *et al* 2019). The CI stimulates the auditory nerve following a stimulation pattern that resembles the speech envelope. The speech envelope is therefore transmitted through slow temporal modulations that leak into the EEG that can obscure the neural recordings (e.g. Hoffman and Wouters 2010, Deprez *et al* 2017, Somers *et al* 2018). Even if some methods have been

proposed to reduce the CI artifact for neural tracking paradigms to single speakers, the artifact cannot be completely removed (Somers *et al* 2019).

Neural tracking can also be measured in a competing talker situation using a so called selective attention paradigm. In this case, the listener is asked to attend to one speaker and ignore all others. Previous studies have shown the possibility to decode selective attention using the forward or the backward model in NH listeners (Mirkovic *et al* 2015, O'Sullivan *et al* 2015) and in CI users (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b, Paul *et al* 2020). A potential advantage of the selective attention paradigm is that it offers the possibility to analyze relative changes in neural activity between the attended and the unattended speech stream. These relative changes in neural activity can be computed as the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients. If both speech streams are properly balanced, it can be assumed that the contribution of each speech stream to the CI artifact will be similar and that the difference between the correlation coefficients will cancel out its effects to some extent.

In order to investigate the relation between speech understanding performance and selective attention decoding in each individual CI user it is convenient to use different signal to interference ratios (SIRs) for both measures. However, different SIRs are created by either increasing or decreasing the target speech level with respect to the interference level or vice versa. For this reason, the proportion of the CI artifact leaking into the EEG caused by the target or the interference speech will vary with SIR. To minimize the effect of the CI artifact at different SIRs, this work suggests recording EEG also at negative SIRs, even if most CI users are not able to understand and attend the target speaker. In the case that the subjects were not able to understand the target speech stream, they were asked to ignore both streams, and therefore this work hypothesizes that at negative SIRs, the EEG will mostly contain CI artifact and no neural activity associated with selective attention will be present in the EEG. Therefore, subtracting the selective attention correlation coefficients recorded at a given SIR and its opposite SIR, i.e. at $-SIR$, will cancel out the CI artifact, at least to some extent. In addition, it can also be hypothesized that the difference in correlation coefficients may be less influenced by the quality of the recorded EEG, which depends, among other factors, on the electrode impedances. Based on these hypotheses, this work will investigate if the attended correlation coefficient as well as the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at the same and opposite SIR derived from a selective attention paradigm can predict speech understanding in NH listeners and CI users.

The envelope of speech is reconstructed across time using shifted versions of the EEG. These shifts are termed lags and represent the physiological delay

between the presented speech stream and its processing across the auditory pathway. In this regard, it has been shown that maximum differences between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients occur at latencies ranging from 200 to 400 ms after stimulus onset for CI users (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b, Paul *et al* 2020). At these later lags the effect of the CI electrical artifact is smaller than at earlier lags, which potentially enables the use of a selective attention paradigm to predict speech understanding in CI users. Moreover, Paul *et al* (2020) investigated whether neural differentiation of attended and ignored speech at an early cortical processing stage of 150 ms or at a late cortical stage of 250 ms can predict speech intelligibility in a group of NH people and bilateral CI users presenting a digit-in-noise test diotically. Enhancement of the attended speech was observed near ~ 150 ms for NH controls, whereas in bilateral CI users higher differentiation between the attended and the ignored speech was observed near ~ 250 ms. Furthermore, Paul *et al* (2020) showed that speech understanding performance can be significantly predicted in bilateral CI users, but not in NH individuals because the behavioural task was too easy for latter group causing ceiling effects. So far, to our knowledge, selective attention decoding in CI users has only been investigated in bilateral CI users presenting concurrent speech streams diotically. However, CI outcome measures in the clinic consist of monaurally presented speech. It remains a question whether it is possible to decode the attended speaker when both speech streams are presented to the same CI side. Moreover, these previous studies with CI users did not investigate the effect of changing the relative presentation levels between the attended and the unattended speech streams or SIR on selective attention decoding.

It is possible that the correlation coefficients from a selective attention paradigm may be influenced by many factors including the materials used to train and test the decoder and the characteristics of the attended and unattended voices. This work investigates the relation between the selective attention correlation coefficients and speech understanding performance. For this purpose, a selective attention decoding paradigm based on a clinically used speech sentence material has been designed. Speech materials that are typically used in the clinical routine have been designed to accurately measure speech understanding performance using balanced lists of sentences and trying to reduce the test re-test variability of the test (e.g. Hey *et al* 2014). Moreover, the use of the same clinical speech material for both the behavioral and the electrophysiological tasks allows for a direct comparison between both measures. Furthermore, EEG was simultaneously recorded to the presentation of a story book in quiet. We study the effect that different types of training material have on the selective attention correlation coefficients. The different

training materials are based on sentences lists only, on the story book only or the combination of both. Moreover, the effect of voice on the selective attention correlation coefficients is investigated. During the selective attention paradigm half of the target sentences lists correspond to a male speaker and the other half correspond to a female speaker. This allows us to investigate the impact of the uttered voice on the selective attention decoding by creating decoders based only on the male or the female speech material.

This work investigates whether it is possible to decode selective attention in CI users by monaural presentation of attended and unattended speech streams. Moreover, this work investigates the possibility to predict speech understanding performance from the attended or from the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at the same or at opposite SIRs. Besides this, the impact of the training material and the gender of the attended talker on selective attention decoding is investigated.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Participants

Ten CI users participated in the study. All patients were native German speakers. CI users were recruited from the clinical database of the Hannover Medical School (MHH) based on their clinical speech intelligibility scores in quiet and in noise. All CI users had more than 6 months experience with their device at the time of measurement. Average age for CI users was 47.4 years (ranging from 24 to 75). More details about the CI users that participated in the study are provided in table 1. As a control group, five NH listeners participated in the study (mean age = 26.8). NH participants did not report any hearing loss. Prior to the experiment, all participants provided written informed consent and the study was carried out in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki principles, approved by the Ethics Committee of the Hannover Medical School.

2.2. Behavioral speech understanding performance

The first experiment consisted of a speech intelligibility test. The speech material was based on the original German HSM sentence test (Hochmair-Desoyer *et al* 1997) uttered by a male voice and a recorded version of the HSM test uttered by a female target voice. Each participant was asked to recall the HSM sentences from a target speaker in the presence of a competing voice. When the target talker was a male voice the competing talker was a female voice and vice versa. After each sentence a short silent pause was inserted to give enough time for the participants to verbally repeat back the sentence. As a measure of speech understanding, the percentage of correctly repeated words for each condition was calculated.

Table 1. Subject data with ID, gender, age at testing for the present study, implant, sound processor, duration of device use, etiology of deafness and clinical speech-in quiet scores using the Hochmair Schulz Moser (HSM) sentence test. M = male, F = female, AB = advanced bionics.

ID	Gender	Age at testing (years)	Implant	Sound processor	Duration of device use (years)	Etiology of deafness	HSM speech-in-quiet scores
CI 1	M	65	AB	Harmony	12	Unknown	66.03%
CI 2	M	24	AB	Naida CI Q90	3	Unknown	85.84%
CI 3	M	35	AB	Naida CI Q90	13	Unknown	100%
CI 4	M	52	AB	Naida CI Q90	19	Genetic	97.16%
CI 5	M	28	Cochlear	CP910	26	Meningitis	100%
CI 6	F	49	AB	Naida CI Q90	10	Unknown	89.62%
CI 7	M	59	Cochlear	CP1000	9	Unknown	99.05%
CI 8	M	28	Cochlear	CP910	26	Unknown	94.33%
CI 9	M	75	AB	Naida CI Q90	13	Genetic	71.7%
CI 10	M	59	MEDEL	Opus2	7	Sudden hearing los	93.9%

In total, 20 lists were presented, ten with the male target voice and the other ten with the female voice. Each four lists (two with male target and two with female target) were presented at a given SIR. In total, five different SIRs were used (SIR = +20 dB, +15 dB, +10 dB, +5 dB, 0 dB). Sentences at negative SIRs were not provided to CI users during the behavioral paradigm, as those SIRs would have been too challenging for them and the speech score would have been close to zero percent. The SIR was manipulated by modifying the level of the interference while keeping the level of the target speaker fixed. The speech material was administered only to one ear. The best hearing side of each subject was selected for the audio presentation. The sound was provided via direct input cable between the audio system and the speech processor for the CI users. For the NH control group, sound was presented through inner-ear headphones (3M E-A-RTONE 3A, 50 Ohm). Stimulus presentation was controlled by the Presentation Software (Neurobehavioral Systems, Inc., Berkeley, CA, United States; version 20.1) as in our previous work (Nogueira *et al* 2019a; 2019b). Every participant adjusted the presentation level to ‘comfortably loud’ by means of a ten-point loudness-rating scale (where 1 was ‘very soft’, 7 was equivalent to ‘comfortably loud’ and 10 was ‘extremely loud’).

2.3. Selective attention decoding procedure

2.3.1. EEG procedure

The second experiment consisted of continuous EEG recorded while speech stimuli were presented to the study participants. Each participant was instructed to sit relaxed and calm, keep their eyes open, and maintain their gaze fixed to the front by looking to a cross displayed on a screen placed in front of the subject. High density EEG data was recorded in an electromagnetically and acoustically shielded booth using a BrainAmp System (Brain Products GmbH, Gilching, Germany) with 96 Ag/AgCl electrodes mounted in a customized, intracerebral electrode cap with an equidistant electrode layout (Easycap GmbH,

Herrsching, Germany). The nose tip of the study participant served as reference while the ground electrode was placed on a central frontopolar site. Data were recorded with a sampling rate of 500 Hz and an online filter from 0.2 to 250 Hz. Impedances were controlled and maintained below 10 k Ω . A delay between the stimulus onset and the trigger captured by the BrainAmp EEG system was measured prior to the experiment and resulted in 77 ms. The jittering between trials was in the order of a few μ s and therefore negligible. The 77 ms delay was compensated in all further analysis.

2.3.2. EEG artifact rejection

The analysis was performed through the EEGLAB toolbox embedded in MATLAB (version 19.0.0b). EEGLAB is an interactive Matlab toolbox for processing continuous and event-related EEG, MEG and other electrophysiological data incorporating independent component analysis (ICA; Delorme and Makeig). ICA was applied to the EEG collected from CI users but not on the data collected from the NH control group. Artifact rejection was conducted according to the two-steps procedure described by Viola *et al* (2012). As a first step, Infomax ICA weights were calculated. Infomax ICA finds independent signals by maximizing entropy (Bell and Sejnowski 1995, Nadal and Parga 1999). The ICA components that presented a physiological artifact were manually determined and rejected. The second step included the determination and rejection of the electrical artifact caused by the CI. Afterwards, the data was split in consecutive intervals corresponding to the length of each list, resulting in 40 trials for each subject.

2.3.3. EEG and speech envelope preprocessing

The EEG was preprocessed in MATLAB 8.1.0.604 (R2018b; Mathworks, Natick, MA, United States) by filtering it using a band-pass filter from 2 to 8 Hz and down sampling to 64 Hz following the same procedure as Nogueira *et al* (2019). The envelopes of the

Table 2. Description of the correlation coefficients and corresponding equations and symbols used along the manuscript.

Description	Equation	Symbol
Attended correlation coefficient across SIR	$\rho_{A_{SIR}}$	ρ_A
Unattended correlation coefficient across SIR	$\rho_{U_{SIR}}$	ρ_U
Difference between attended and unattended correlation coefficient at the same SIR	$\rho_{A_{SIR}} - \rho_{U_{SIR}}$	ρ_{Diff}
Difference between attended and unattended correlation coefficient at opposite SIR	$\rho_{A_{SIR}} - \rho_{U_{-SIR}}$	$\rho_{DiffOpp}$

original audio material (HSM and story book) were estimated based on the Hilbert transform of the original audio signal. The audio signals likewise were low-pass filtered (8 Hz) and down sampled to 64 Hz.

Speech reconstruction from EEG was obtained through the backward model of neural responses (mTRF; Crosse *et al* 2016). The linear modeling performs a least square estimation between neural data and the stimulus to reconstruct an envelope of the signal. The reconstructed envelope was correlated to the envelope of the original attended audio stream (attended correlation coefficient; ρ_A) and to the original unattended audio stream (unattended correlation coefficient; ρ_U). The regularization parameter was set to 0.01 as in our previous study (Nogueira *et al* 2019). A leave-one-out cross validation was conducted resulting in 40 folds, which corresponds to the amount of presented HSM lists (for more details to procedure see Nogueira *et al* 2019). Only HSM lists were used for the testing. The chance level was estimated from the correlation coefficients between the reconstructed speech stream for a particular HSM list and the envelope speech stream of other randomly selected HSM lists. The chance correlation coefficient level was estimated from 40 HSM lists (20 uttered by the male and 20 uttered by the female voice) corresponding to 40 folds of the cross-validation procedure. The correlation coefficients were calculated for different lags, representing the time shifted versions of the EEG signal. The interval from 16 to 520 ms was analyzed using 16 ms lag windows. The first lag window ranged from 0 to 16 ms. For the further analysis, correlation coefficients were averaged across the lag interval 226–300 ms. This lag interval was chosen to minimize the effect of the CI artifact.

The stimuli consisted of lists of sentences from the HSM test, different to the ones used during the speech intelligibility test, but with additional SIR conditions. In total, nine SIRs were presented: -20 dB, -15 dB, -10 dB, -5 dB, 0 dB, $+5$ dB, $+10$ dB, $+15$ dB, $+20$ dB. Each SIR included four lists (two lists with the male voice and two lists with the female voice as target) except for the 0 dB SIR, which included eight lists. In total, 40 lists were presented. Positive SIRs were created keeping the level of the target speaker fixed and modifying the level of the interference. In contrast, negative SIRs were created modifying the level of the target speaker while keeping the level of the interferer fixed. Because speech understanding at negative SIRs is very challenging for CI users, subjects

were instructed to ignore both speech streams if they were not able to attend the target speaker. Therefore, at negative SIRs it can be assumed that the EEG contains mainly CI artifact rather than neural activity associated to selective attention. Based on this methodology, the level of the attended speech at a given positive SIR is exactly the same as the level of the unattended speech stream at the opposite SIR (i.e. SIR) and therefore their contribution to the CI artifact should be similar. Subtracting the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at opposite SIR ($\rho_{A_{SIR}} - \rho_{U_{-SIR}}$) would reduce the effect of the CI artifact and could open the possibility to analyze its relation to speech understanding performance. We denote the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at the same and at the opposite SIR with the symbols ρ_{Diff} and $\rho_{DiffOpp}$, respectively. Table 2 summarizes the selective attention correlation coefficients used in the current study.

The EEG procedure was conducted without requiring repetition of the words by the study participants. Moreover, EEG to a 16 min long story (English: ‘A drama in the air’ by Jules Verne) narrated by a single male voice in German was recorded. This additional recording was used to increase the amount of data to train the decoder. The story was presented in absence of noise. The speech material was presented monaurally to the better hearing side of the CI users. The CI sound processor was moved from their usual position (behind the ear) to the participant’s collar. The change in placement did not affect the participant’s sound perception with the CI, as the sound was delivered via a direct audio cable.

2.4. Factors influencing selective attention decoding in CI users

2.4.1. Effect of training material on selective attention decoding

To investigate the impact of the training material on selective attention decoding, different decoders were designed. In total three decoders were created based on the training speech material: HSM (Decoder_{HSM}), the story book (Decoder_{Story}) and the combination of both (Decoder_{HSM+Story}). The idea behind the Decoder_{HSM} is to create a balanced decoder in which the amount of speech used to train the decoder is the same at each SIR. In contrast, the Decoder_{Story} is trained using only a single speaker. The Decoder_{HSM+Story} is trained using both a single speaker and the HSM at different SIRs. The

Decoder_{Story} and Decoder_{HSM+Story} may introduce a bias when testing the decoders with the HSM at different SIRs, because with increasing SIR, the test material will become more similar to most of the training material based on a single speech stream. For the three decoders, only HSM sentences were used as a testing material.

2.4.2. Effect of voice on selective attention decoding

In order to investigate the impact of the uttered voice on the correlation coefficients, two additional decoders based only on male target sentences Decoder_{HSM_Male} or only on female target sentences Decoder_{HSM_Female} were created and compared. Note, that for training and testing decoder only HSM sentences were used.

2.4.3. Selective attention decoding through monaural presentation of speech in CI users

To investigate selective attention decoding in CI users when both speech streams were presented monaurally, the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at the chosen lag window (226–300 ms) were compared at each SIR through the statistical *t*-test.

2.4.4. Effect of SIR on selective attention decoding

The effect of SIR on the correlation coefficients from selective attention decoding was investigated through Spearman correlation. For this purpose, the attended correlation coefficients (ρ_A), the unattended correlation coefficients (ρ_U), and the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at the same SIR (ρ_{Diff}) and at the opposite SIR ($\rho_{DiffOpp}$) were used as measures of selective attention decoding.

2.5. Correlation between selective attention decoding and speech understanding performance in CI users

The correlation coefficient between behavioral speech understanding performance and the coefficients of selective attention decoding was obtained through repeated measures correlation (Bakdash *et al* 2019), which can be used to determine within-individual correlations for paired measures assessed on two or more occasions without averaging data across SIRs.

2.6. Statistical analysis

To investigate the effect of training material, the effect of voice and the effect of SIR on the selective attention correlation coefficients a repeated measures analysis of variance (rm-ANOVA), as implemented in the SPSS Software version 27 (IBM, Armonk, NY, USA), was conducted. Pairwise comparisons were conducted through post-hoc *t*-tests. To avoid type I error for multiple comparisons, Bonferroni correction was applied. In case the data was non-normally distributed, a non-parametric Friedman test followed by

post-hoc Wilcoxon tests were used. The effect of SIR on the selective attention correlation coefficients was investigated through Spearman correlation. The possibility to predict speech understanding performance in CI users from the selective attention correlation coefficients was investigated through multiple correlation analysis (Bakdash and Marusich 2019).

3. Results

3.1. Behavioral speech understanding performance

Figure 1 presents the behaviorally measured speech understanding scores across SIRs for the CI users that participated in the study. Note, that the behavioral test was not conducted at negative SIRs, because most subjects would not be able to perform the task.

At some SIRs, the data was not normally distributed based on the Shapiro–Wilk test. For this reason, a non-parametric Friedman test was conducted to assess the impact of SIR on speech understanding performance. The test revealed a significant effect of SIR: $\chi^2(4) = 37.005$, $p < 0.0001$. The speech scores at consecutive SIRs were compared in pairs using a Wilcoxon signed rank test with Bonferroni correction resulting in a significance level of $p = 0.0125$. All consecutive pairs were significantly different ($p < 0.0125$) except the pair SIR = +20 dB vs SIR = +15 dB ($p = 0.028$).

To assess the effect of voice gender, a Wilcoxon signed rank test was conducted between the speech scores obtained when the CI user listened to the male and to the female speaker at each SIR. No significant difference was observed between the speech scores obtained when the CI users listened to the male or the female voice at any SIR.

3.2. Selective attention decoding in CI users

3.2.1. Effect of training material on selective attention decoding

Figure 2 presents the attended and unattended correlation coefficients across lags (Δ) for each decoder Decoder_{HSM}, Decoder_{HSM+Story}, Decoder_{Story} and for different SIRs after applying ICA for CI artifact reduction. The grey shaded areas denote the chance level. In appendix A, the same data is presented before applying ICA artifact rejection for the Decoder_{HSM}. The ICA rejection caused reduction of the unattended correlation coefficients, especially at negative SIRs. For comparison, data in appendix B presents the correlation coefficients across lags in NH listeners.

In figure 2, the morphology of the curve representing the attended correlation coefficient presents relatively large values above 0.1 for lags below ~200 ms. This relatively large correlation coefficient may be explained by the effect of residual CI artifact leaking into the EEG. After 200 ms, the correlation coefficient drops rapidly and the curve presents two peaks. Further analysis of the correlation

coefficients focused on the lag window ranging from 226 to 300 ms.

To investigate the influence of the training material, the statistical analysis was performed on the mentioned lag interval for the three different decoders ($\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM}}$, $\text{Decoder}_{\text{Story}}$, $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM+Story}}$). A two-way-rm-ANOVA revealed a significant effect of training material ($F(2,18) = 25.0008$, $p = 0.001$), of SIR ($F(8,72) = 12.810$, $p < 0.001$) and a significant interaction between both factors ($F(16,144) = 6.028$, $p = 0.001$) on the attended correlation coefficients ρ_A . The post-hoc t -test demonstrated a significant difference for the pairs $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM}}$ and $\text{Decoder}_{\text{Story}}$ ($p = 0.001$) as well as for the pair $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM+Story}}$ and $\text{Decoder}_{\text{Story}}$ ($p < 0.001$) but no significant difference for the pair $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM}}$ and $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM+Story}}$. The impact of the training material on the difference correlation coefficients ρ_{Diff} was also investigated. A two-way-rm-ANOVA revealed a significant effect of training material ($F(2,18) = 18.879$, $p = 0.001$), a significant effect of SIR ($F(8,72) = 8.715$, $p < 0.001$) and a significant interaction between both factors ($F(16,144) = 2.348$, $p = 0.028$) on ρ_{Diff} . Post-hoc t -tests showed a significant difference for all pairs: $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM}}$ and $\text{Decoder}_{\text{Story}}$ ($p = 0.001$), $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM+Story}}$ and $\text{Decoder}_{\text{Story}}$ ($p = 0.002$) and $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM}}$ and $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM+Story}}$ ($p = 0.014$).

For further analysis, the $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM}}$ was selected, because this decoder obtained the highest numerical attended correlation coefficients and resulted in significantly higher difference correlation coefficients

ρ_{Diff} . Moreover, this decoder uses the same training material as the one used for testing and it is balanced in terms of SIR (see section 3.3).

In figure 2, it can be observed that at 0 dB SIR, the correlation coefficient to the attended speech stream was higher than the correlation coefficient to the unattended speech stream. At this SIR condition, the CI artifact may have less impact on the correlation coefficients as the target and interference speech streams were delivered at the same presentation level. However, it cannot be discarded that one of the two voices (male or female) caused an increased artifact explaining the larger correlation coefficient to the attended than to the unattended speech. This effect is investigated in section 4.2.2.

3.2.2. Effect of voice on selective attention decoding

In this section we focus on the $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM}}$ to analyze the correlation coefficients. No significant differences in behaviorally measured speech understanding performance were observed when the CI users attended to the male or to the female target speaker. However, the acoustic characteristics of the two speech streams could have an impact on the neural envelope representation. Figure 3 shows the correlation coefficients across lags for each SIR for $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM_Male}}$ and for $\text{Decoder}_{\text{HSM_Female}}$.

A two-way-rm-ANOVA was conducted to assess the effect of voice (male or female) and SIR on the averaged attended correlation coefficients ρ_A and difference correlation coefficients ρ_{Diff} in the lag range

Figure 2. Correlation coefficients (Corr Coeff) across lags (Δ) to the attended (ρ_A) and the unattended (ρ_U) speech stream for CI users at different SIRs and for different training materials: (top) story book, (center) HSM test and (bottom) story book + HSM test. Selective attention was decoded for SIRs ranging from -20 dB to $+20$ dB SIR. Thick lines represent mean across subjects, shaded areas represent standard deviation. The grey shaded areas show the chance level.

from 226 ms to 300 ms. The ANOVA showed no significant effect of voice ($F(1, 9) = 4.375, p = 0.058$), a significant effect of SIR ($F(8, 72) = 14.113, p < 0.001$) and no significant interaction between both factors

($F(8, 72) = 1.531, p = 0.168$) on the attended correlation coefficients (ρ_A) and no significant effect of voice ($F(1, 9) = 2.817, p = 0.128$), a significant effect of SIR ($F(8, 72) = 6.085, p < 0.001$) and no significant

Figure 3. Attended (ρ_A) and the unattended (ρ_U) correlation coefficients for CI users at different SIRs. The testing material used to compute the correlation coefficients consisted of the HSM sentence test uttered by a male (top panel) or a female (bottom panel) voice. Selective attention was decoded for SIRs ranging from -20 dB to $+20$ dB. The training material was based on the HSM sentence test to create the decoder Decoder_{HSM}. Thick lines represent mean across subjects, shaded areas represent standard deviation. The grey shaded areas show the chance level.

interaction between both factors ($F(8, 72) = 0.827$, $p = 0.577$) on the difference correlation coefficients (ρ_{Diff}).

In general, the morphology of the correlation coefficients across lags does not present a substantial difference between the male and the female voice. Based on the outcomes of the statistical analysis, the hypothesis about impact of voice on selective attention decoding was rejected and the correlation coefficients for both, the male and the female speech stream, were combined for further analysis.

3.2.3. Selective attention decoding through monaural presentation of speech in CI users

Figure 4 presents the correlation coefficients to the attended (ρ_A) and to the unattended (ρ_U) speech stream for CI users at different SIRs averaged across the lag interval 226–300 ms. A significant difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients for SIRs larger or equal to 0 dB was found ($p < 0.05$). Still, it is worth mentioning that at SIR = -5 dB the difference between the attended the unattended correlation coefficient just missed

significance ($p = 0.055$). The obtained p -values of the t -test are included in figure 4. For more negative SIRs below -5 dB, no significant differences between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients were observed, probably because at these conditions, CI users could not focus on the attended speech.

It is important to remark that if the artifact would be the only factor contributing to the correlation coefficients of selective attention decoding, one would expect similar values for the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at SIR = 0 dB. From these results, it can be concluded that it is possible to decode selective attention in CI when the target and the interference speech are presented monaurally to the same ear.

3.2.4. Effect of SIR on selective attention decoding

This section investigates the attended ρ_A and unattended ρ_U correlation coefficients across SIRs as well as the difference between both correlation coefficients (ρ_{Diff}). Note that the SIR ranged from -20 to $+20$ dB and at positive SIRs the level of the target signal was kept constant while the level of the interference was

Figure 4. Correlation coefficients (ρ_A , ρ_U) to the attended and to the unattended speech stream for CI users at different SIRs averaged across the lag interval 226–300 ms. Grey lines with p value show the result of the t -test for pairs of attended and unattended correlation coefficients at each SIR. The asterisks denote significance.

reduced. In contrast, for negative SIRs, the level of the interferer was kept constant while the level of the target was decreased. If residual CI artifact leaks into the EEG, it is expected that the correlation coefficient to the attended speech or to the difference between both correlation coefficients will increase with SIR. For this reason, we also analyzed the difference between the attended correlation coefficient at a given SIR and the unattended correlation coefficient at the opposite SIR (ρ_{DiffOpp}). We hypothesized that ρ_{DiffOpp} balances the effect of residual CI electrical artifact for each SIRs.

The correlation coefficient to the attended speech stream (ρ_A ; top left panel) and to the unattended speech stream (ρ_U ; top right panel), as well as the difference correlation coefficient between the attended and unattended speech stream at the same (ρ_{Diff} ; bottom left panel) and at opposite SIRs (ρ_{DiffOpp} ; bottom right panel) averaged across lags ranging from 226 to 300 ms are presented in figure 5.

The results of figure 5 show that ρ_A , ρ_{Diff} , and ρ_{DiffOpp} become larger with increasing SIR. To investigate this, a Spearman correlation between SIR and the correlation coefficients was calculated. A significant correlation between SIR and ρ_A ($r = 0.967$, $p < 0.0001$), between SIR and ρ_{Diff} ($r = 0.850$, $p = 0.004$), and between SIR and ρ_{DiffOpp} ($r = 0.917$, $p = 0.001$) was observed. No significant correlation was found between SIR and the unattended correlation coefficient ($r = 0.217$, $p = 0.576$).

3.3. Correlation between selective attention decoding and speech understanding performance in CI users

Figure 6 presents the correlation analysis between speech understanding scores in percentage of correct words and the selective attention correlation coefficients: ρ_A , ρ_U , ρ_{Diff} , and ρ_{DiffOpp} for each individual subject across SIRs. The speech understanding performance was measured only at positive SIR conditions, as the negative SIR conditions were too challenging for CI users and the speech score would have been zero percent.

The results from figure 6 show that in general the repeated measures correlation coefficients tend to increase with higher speech understanding performance. Significant repeated measures correlations between speech understanding scores and selective attention decoding were observed for ρ_A ($r = 0.594$; $p < 0.001$), for ρ_U ($r = 0.439$; $p = 0.004$) and for ρ_{DiffOpp} ($r = 0.515$, $p < 0.001$).

4. Discussion

This work investigated the possibility to decode selective attention in CI users when two speech streams are presented monaurally and at different SIRs. Moreover, this study investigated the influence of using different types of training and test material and the effect of the target voice on the

correlation coefficients derived from a selective attention paradigm. The end goal of the present work was to investigate whether behavioral speech understanding performance can be predicted from the selective attention correlation coefficients at different SIR levels.

4.1. Selective attention decoding through monaural presentation of speech in CI users

Previous research showed that it is possible to decode selective attention in NH listeners through dichotic (e.g. Mirkovic *et al* 2015, O'Sullivan *et al* 2015) and monaural presentation of two concurrent speech streams (e.g. Mesgarani *et al* 2012, Ciccarelli *et al* 2019). In CI users, Somers *et al* (2019) showed that it is possible to conduct EEG neural tracking when a single monaural speech stream with background noise is used. Moreover, previous studies showed the possibility to decode selective attention in bilateral CI users through dichotic presentation of two concurrent speech streams (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b), by presenting each speech stream through an independent loudspeaker (Paul *et al* 2020) or by presenting the two speech streams monaurally to the acoustic side of single-sided deaf CI users while recording the EEG with the CI as sensor (Aldag *et al* 2022). The current study extends these previous works and shows that it is also possible to decode selective attention when both speech streams are monaurally presented to CI users. Moreover, selective attention was decoded at

positive and negative SIRs computing the correlation coefficients between the reconstructed speech and the attended or the unattended speech stream. As expected, the attended correlation coefficients are lower for NH listeners than for CI users, probably because the CI transmits envelope information in each electrode and the CI stimulation leaks into the EEG as artifact. Note that neural tracking or selective attention correlation scores are usually modest (on the order of 0.1 and 0.2 for EEG data). The main reason is that EEG signals reflect many brain processes in addition to those related to sensory processing, and thus only a fraction of the EEG variance can be predicted from the stimulus (Woodman 2010, de Cheveigné *et al* 2018).

The results of the current study show that the attended correlation coefficient presented two peaks at around 170 and 250 ms for CI users (figure 2) and for NH listeners (figure 7 of appendix B). These peaks became smoother with decreasing SIR. Results from our previous studies (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b) show that these two peaks were only observed for NH listeners and not for CI users when the SIR was 0 dB. Therefore, the appearance of these two peaks may be caused by the use of higher SIR conditions in the current study which made the task easier for the CI users. In agreement with the same previous works (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b), high correlation coefficients in the range of 0.1–0.4 were observed for CI users at early lags. The correlation coefficients

at these early lag intervals are probably more contaminated by the electrical artifact. In previous studies we showed that the correlation coefficients drop rapidly with increasing lags (Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b). If the EEG signal contains mainly CI artifact related to the envelope of the incoming speech signal, the decoder is in practice conducting a correlation of the speech signal with itself. Therefore, the decrease of the selective attention correlation coefficient with lag may be expected, as the autocorrelation of speech decreases rapidly. This effect was demonstrated using a decoder trained with simulated EEG signals or using a very simple model to characterize the artifact (see Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b for more details). Consistent with these previous findings, the first peak of the attended correlation coefficient was observed at lag 170 ms and it was higher than the second peak observed at lag 250 ms. Therefore, it can be assumed that the second peak is less contaminated by the CI electrical artifact. The use of later lags was also suggested by the TRF analysis performed by Paul *et al* (2020), who showed that late cortical responses (around 250 ms) are more suitable to decode selective attention and can predict speech intelligibility in comparison to early cortical responses at 150 ms in

bilateral CI users. Moreover, the chosen time interval coincides with the latency associated to the modulation of the impulse response directed by attention (Power *et al* 2012). Therefore, we focused our analysis on the correlation coefficients at later lags (226–300 ms) corresponding with second peak and minimizing the effect of the CI artifact.

The results of the current study showed significantly higher correlation coefficients to the attended speech stream than to the unattended speech stream for positive SIRs in CI users. Increasing positive SIRs were created by keeping the level of the attended speech stream fixed and decreasing the level of the unattended speech stream. For this reason, it was expected that the correlation coefficient to the attended speech stream would become higher with increasing SIR, as the person may be able to focus better on the target speaker. It is remarkable that at 0 dB SIR, where the contribution of the attended and the unattended speech stream to the CI artifact is similar, the attended correlation coefficients were significantly higher than unattended ones ($p = 0.010$). Moreover, at -5 dB SIR the numerical value of the attended correlation coefficient was higher than the unattended one and the difference between both just

missed significance ($p = 0.055$). These results demonstrate that it is possible to decode selective attention from EEG when two concurrent speech streams are presented monaurally to CI users.

4.2. Factors influencing selective attention decoding

4.2.1. Effect of training material

In previous studies, the speech materials used for training and testing the decoder were based on the same story books (e.g. O'Sullivan *et al* 2015, Mirkovic *et al* 2015, Nogueira *et al* 2019a, 2019b) or the same digit-in-noise test (Paul *et al* 2020). In contrast, Lesenfants *et al* (2019) used a story book uttered by a single voice for training the decoder and sentences in noise to test the decoder. In the current work, the effect of using different speech materials for training and testing the decoders was investigated. Three decoders were designed for this purpose: the first one was trained using a story book (Decoder_{Story}), the second one was trained based on HSM sentences (Decoder_{HSM}) and the third one was trained based on both, the story book and the HSM sentences (Decoder_{HSM+Story}). The three decoders were tested using HSM sentences at different SIRs. The results of the investigation show that the training material had a significant effect on the attended correlation coefficient ($p = 0.001$) and on the difference correlation coefficients ($p = 0.001$). The Decoder_{Story} used the most different materials between training and testing and resulted in the lowest attended correlation coefficients. It is interesting to note that with the Decoder_{Story}, the attended correlation coefficient gradually became higher with increasing SIR (figure 2), probably because the training material used to create this decoder was more similar to the test material conditions with higher SIRs. It is possible that the Decoder_{HSM} introduces a bias in the results which depends on the acoustic similarity between training and testing material. The attended correlation coefficients obtained with the Decoder_{HSM} and the Decoder_{HSM+Story} were numerically very similar. However, the statistical analysis revealed that the difference correlation coefficients (ρ_{Diff}) were significantly higher for the Decoder_{HSM} than for the Decoder_{HSM+Story} ($p = 0.014$). Moreover, the material used to train and test the Decoder_{HSM} is balanced in terms of SIR, meaning that the decoder is trained with the same amount of speech at positive and negative SIRs. For this reason, we selected the Decoder_{HSM} for further analysis in our study.

4.2.2. Effect of voice

In the current work we used a speech material uttered by a male and by a female voice to facilitate the distinction between the target and the interference speech streams. The presentation level of the speech material for both voices was balanced, however differences in acoustic characteristics between the male

and the female speech stream such as the fundamental frequency, modulation depth, clarity or other factors could have an impact on the representation of speech envelope in the neural activity. In this regard, a previous study by van Canneyt *et al* (2020) investigated neural tracking of fundamental frequency from EEG using a specific paradigm and showed significant differences between target male and target female speech streams. In contrast, the current study used a selective attention paradigm to reconstruct the speech envelope from cortical activity and we did not observe significant differences in neural responses to the male or the female voice, which is consistent with the results from Kong *et al* (2014) using a similar paradigm.

4.2.3. Effect of SIR

It is known that the CI introduces an electrical artifact that leaks into the EEG and that this artifact is related to the speech envelope. However, the artifact produced by speech signals is weaker than the artifact introduced by more deterministic stimuli such as pulse trains or pure tones (Wagner *et al* 2018). An advantage of the selective attention paradigm w.r.t. neural tracking paradigms to single stimuli is that it can be used to analyze the differences between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients. Assuming similar artifact contributions from both speech streams and after using late lags for the analysis as well as ICA artifact removal, it is expected that the differences between both correlation coefficients are dominated by neural activity rather than by the CI artifact. The effect of SIR on selective attention decoding was investigated in previous research (Lesenfants *et al* 2019) and showed higher correlation coefficients with increasing SIR in NH listeners. In the present work, the attended correlation coefficient ρ_A measured in CI users became higher with increasing SIR, which confirms this previous work. Moreover, the attended and the unattended correlation coefficient difference ρ_{Diff} became larger with increasing SIRs. However, it is possible that this increase in ρ_A or in ρ_{Diff} is caused by residual CI leaking into the EEG. The reason being that positive SIRs were created by reducing the level of the unattended speech stream while keeping constant the level of the attended speech stream, and hence the contribution of the unattended speech to the CI artifact will be less with increasing SIR. For this reason, we introduced a new method that may be less influenced by the CI artifact. The new method uses the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at opposite SIRs (ρ_{DiffOpp}). Negative SIRs were created keeping the level of the unattended speech and reducing the level of the attended speech. Hence, the subtraction of the attended and unattended correlation coefficients at opposite SIRs should balance any residual effect of the CI artifact. The results of the current study show that this difference between correlation coefficients increased with greater SIR.

4.3. Relation between speech understanding and selective attention decoding

A goal of the present study was to predict speech understanding performance based on the correlation coefficients derived from the selective attention decoding paradigm. Paul *et al* (2020) showed that it is possible to predict speech understanding performance of CI users from the TRF at a fixed SIR when late cortical responses (250 ms) are used, but these results could not be confirmed in NH listeners. The present study measured behavioral speech understanding performance and selective attention decoding presenting two concurrent speech streams at different SIRs using the same speech material for both tasks. The speech performance of CI users was measured only at positive SIRs, as the negative SIR conditions were too challenging for them. The results of the current study showed a significant correlation between the attended correlation coefficient ρ_A and the behaviorally measured speech understanding performance ($r = 0.594$; $p < 0.001$). However, it cannot be completely excluded that this result is explained by residual CI artifact, even if ICA rejection was applied and late lags were used for the analysis. For this reason, this work also analyzed the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at opposite SIRs (ρ_{DiffOpp}), a condition that in principle balances the contribution of the CI artifact in the recorded EEG. The correlation coefficient ρ_{DiffOpp} presented a significant correlation with speech understanding performance ($r = 0.515$, $p < 0.001$). It is important to mention that the participants of the study can be considered as good CI performers, therefore it would be interesting to extend the present study to poor performance CI users. Moreover, the majority of the CI users in the current study were male participants. In previous studies, where the CI users and NH were balanced in terms of gender, we observed very similar morphologies for the curves representing the correlation coefficients across lags for both the attended and the unattended speech streams. Although it cannot be completely discarded that the results of the current study do not generalize for a more gender balanced population of CI users, we would expect similar results if more female CI users would have been recruited.

Recent advances have shown that it is possible to record cortical potentials and perform neural tracking (Somers *et al* 2021) or selective attention decoding (Aldag *et al* 2022) from inside the cochlea using the CI as a sensor device. Such a system does not require additional hardware to record EEG and can be easily applied in a clinical environment. The selective attention paradigm proposed in the current study could be combined with EEG recorded from the CI to develop a closed-loop CI with neuro-feedback functionality.

5. Conclusion

The results of the study confirm that it is possible to decode selective attention in CI users even if continuous artifact is present in the recordings. Moreover, the results show that it is possible to decode selective attention when two concurrent speech streams are presented monaurally to CI users. The study demonstrates that the selection of the type of material for training the selective attention decoder significantly influences the results. Meanwhile, no effect of gender of the target voice on the correlation coefficients was observed. In general, it was shown that the correlation coefficient to the attended speech stream or the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients increase with SIR. However, it cannot be completely excluded that these effects are caused by residual CI artifact leaking into the EEG. The current study presents a novel measure based on the difference between the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients at opposite SIRs which further balances the residual CI artifact. The suggested measure showed a significant correlation with the speech understanding performance of the CI users.

Data availability statement

The data generated and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly available for legal/ethical reasons but are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Ethical statement

The study was carried out in accordance with the declaration of Helsinki principles and approved by the ethics committee of the Hannover Medical School (Hanover, Germany). The participants provided their written informed consent to participate in this study.

Appendix A. Decoding selective attention at different signal to interference ratios without artifact rejection

Figure 6 presents the attended and the unattended correlation coefficients of selective attention before applying Infomax ICA artifact rejection averaged across the CI users that participated in the study. Note that positive SIRs were obtained by setting the level of the target speaker and reducing the level of the interferer. In contrast, negative SIRs were obtained by setting the level of the interferer and reducing the level of the target speaker. In figure 6, it can be seen that for negative SIRs, the unattended correlation coefficients are higher than the attended correlation coefficients. This effect can be explained by the higher level of the target stream.

The use of ICA significantly decreases the unattended correlation coefficients, but not the attended correlation coefficients at the positive SIRs. It is also to observe that at 0 dB SIR, where both streams were presented at the same level, the attended correlation coefficients are higher than unattended.

Appendix B. Decoding selective attention in normal hearing listeners

The same measures performed in CI users were also conducted in a control group of five NH listeners

(mean age = 26.8). All NH participants did not have hearing loss. The EEG recordings were obtained using exactly the same methodology as in CI users but presenting the two speech streams via an insert earphone (3M E-A-RTONE 3A, 50 Ohm) monaurally. Each participant adjusted the presentation level to ‘comfortably loud’ level by means of a seven-point loudness-rating scale (where 1 is ‘very soft’ and 7 is ‘extremely loud’). The attended and the unattended correlation coefficients were calculated for the Decoder_{HSM} at nine different SIRs (figure 7).

In figure 7, it can be observed that at early lags, the correlation coefficients for NH listeners presented lower values than for CI users (around 0.04 for NH listeners compared to 0.25 for CI users; figure 8). This large difference may be explained by the contribution of the CI artifact at early lags. Moreover, previous works show larger correlation coefficients for hearing impaired subjects compared to NH listeners (Decruy *et al* 2020). The morphology of the curves is consistent with previous works of Nogueira *et al* (2019a, 2019b) showing two distinguished peaks at lags corresponding with 120 ms and 250 ms. The second peak in the attended correlation coefficient curve can also be observed in the curves obtained in CI users. For this reason, the same lag interval ranging from 225 ms to 300 ms was used in the analysis.

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